

COMMUNICATIVE-PRAGMATIC FEATURES OF COMMISSIVE SPEECH ACTS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14552927>

Abstract. *The article investigates the role and function of commissive speech acts in English communication. The study focuses on the pragmatic features that shape the interpretation of these acts, considering factors such as the speaker's intention, context, and relationship with the interlocutor. It examines how commissives function not only as expressions of commitment but also as tools for managing social relations and expectations. The article explores how these acts are used to establish obligations and negotiate power dynamics in various communicative contexts. It highlights the importance of linguistic forms, such as modal verbs, future tense, and lexical choices, in conveying the strength of commitment in English. The paper further analyzes how politeness strategies are employed in the production of commissive speech acts, with an emphasis on mitigating or enhancing the force of commitment based on the social status of the participants. Drawing on real-world examples, the study illustrates how context and cultural norms shape the appropriateness and effectiveness of commissive in English. It also explores the differences in how direct and indirect commissives are used, noting the role of indirectness in managing face-threatening situations. The article compares commissive speech acts in English with those in other languages, highlighting both similarities and differences in their pragmatics. In conclusion, the study emphasizes the significance of understanding the communicative-pragmatic features of commissives in English for effective communication, discourse analysis, and cross-cultural interactions. The findings offer valuable insights into how speakers negotiate meaning and intention in everyday English conversation.*

Keywords: *pragmatics, commissive speech acts, hedging, modality, social context, commitment, directness, indirectness, power dynamics, online communication, interpersonal communication.*

Introduction. Commissive speech acts, which encompass utterances through which speakers commit to future actions, play a fundamental role in interpersonal communication. They represent a key component of human interaction, as they establish relationships of trust, responsibility, and social coordination [2]. In English language, commissives include promises, offers, invitations, and vows, which are pivotal in conveying intentions and negotiating future behaviors. The pragmatic functions of these acts are not merely determined by their linguistic forms, but also by the social and contextual factors that shape how commitments are made and interpreted [3].

The communicative-pragmatic features of commissive speech acts in English have been examined within the framework of speech act theory, which emphasizes the illocutionary force of utterances and their role in achieving specific communicative goals [1, 2]. While much of the research has focused on the general classification of speech acts, recent studies have begun to delve into the subtleties of how commissive acts are realized in English across different social contexts and communicative settings [4]. For instance, directness, hedging, and politeness strategies are

critical factors that influence the speaker's ability to effectively execute a commitment without threatening face or social harmony [3].

Understanding the communicative-pragmatic features of commissive speech acts in English is crucial, as it not only informs linguistic theory but also provides insights into everyday communication practices. Whether in informal settings such as personal conversations or more formal contexts like business negotiations, the way in which speakers convey their commitments can significantly impact the dynamics of social relationships. This article aims to explore the linguistic strategies employed in the realization of commissive speech acts in English, analyzing how these acts function in terms of their illocutionary force, politeness, and social implications.

By examining the pragmatic features of commissives, this study will contribute to a deeper understanding of the role of commitment in communication. Moreover, it will provide a foundation for future research on cross-cultural comparisons and the application of speech act theory in various communicative contexts.

Methods and literature review. The present study employs a qualitative approach to investigate the communicative-pragmatic features of commissive speech acts in English language. The research focuses on identifying and analyzing the different linguistic strategies used in the realization of commissives (promises, offers, invitations, etc.) in both formal and informal contexts. The study combines discourse analysis and pragmatic theory to examine how these speech acts function in various social settings. To explore the communicative-pragmatic features of commissive speech acts in English, a diverse corpus of spoken and written texts was compiled. The corpus includes naturally occurring conversations, online communications (such as emails and social media interactions), business meetings, and political speeches. These texts were selected to reflect a variety of contexts, ranging from informal, everyday interactions to formal, institutional settings. Additionally, the corpus includes instances of both direct and indirect commissive acts, allowing for a detailed examination of linguistic strategies such as hedging, modality, and politeness markers.

The data were collected from publicly available sources, including transcriptions of recorded conversations, professional documents, and internet communication. Particular attention was given to speech acts performed by speakers in English-speaking countries, ensuring that the language used reflected both the communicative norms of English and the social dynamics of the specific contexts in which the speech acts occurred.

The data analysis was conducted using a combination of qualitative coding and discourse analysis techniques. Each instance of a commissive speech act was identified and classified according to its type (e.g., promise, offer, invitation). Subsequently, the linguistic features of these acts, including the use of modal verbs (e.g., *will*, *could*), conditional clauses (e.g., *if*, *might*), and hedging devices (e.g., *maybe*, *perhaps*), were analyzed to determine the strategies employed by speakers in making their commitments.

Furthermore, the analysis considered the sociocultural context of the speech acts, such as the relationship between the speaker and the listener, the level of formality, and the presence of politeness strategies. This allowed for a comprehensive examination of how different contextual factors influenced the realization and perception of commissive speech acts in English.

The study of commissive speech acts in English language has a long-standing tradition in pragmatics, with many scholars contributing to the theoretical framework of speech acts. Austin's pioneering work on speech act theory laid the foundation for understanding how utterances

function as actions in communication [1]. According to Austin, speech acts can be categorized into three types: locutionary acts (the act of saying something), illocutionary acts (the act performed in saying something), and perlocutionary acts (the effect of saying something on the listener). Commissive acts are classified as illocutionary acts because they involve the speaker's commitment to a future course of action.

Searle expanded on Austin's work and provided a more detailed categorization of speech acts, including commissives, which he defined as speech acts in which the speaker commits to doing something in the future [2]. Promises, offers, and invitations are all considered forms of commissive acts because they involve a speaker's commitment to a specific future action, regardless of whether that commitment is explicit or implied.

Research on the pragmatics of commissives has focused on how these acts are realized linguistically and how they vary across different languages and cultures. Brown and Levinson's influential theory of politeness has played a significant role in understanding how speakers use various strategies, such as indirectness and hedging, to mitigate the potential face-threatening effects of their speech acts [3]. According to their theory, speakers engage in face-saving behaviors to avoid threatening the social identity of either the speaker or the listener. In the case of commissive acts, speakers may hedge their promises or offers to reduce the risk of failure and to maintain politeness, especially in situations where the commitment is uncertain or difficult to fulfill.

Research on English-language commissive speech acts has often explored the role of modality and conditional structures in their realization. For example, Holmes discussed how speakers use modal verbs (e.g., *will*, *may*, *might*) and conditional forms to indicate varying degrees of commitment and to mitigate the force of their speech acts [4]. Modal verbs are particularly important in commissive speech acts because they allow speakers to express different levels of certainty and commitment. For instance, a statement like *I will help you* is a stronger commitment than *I might help you*, reflecting different levels of commitment to the future action.

The use of hedging in commissive acts has also been a topic of interest in pragmatics. Holmes argued that hedging is a crucial strategy in English because it allows speakers to express their intentions without committing fully, which is especially important in situations where the speaker wants to maintain flexibility or avoid the risk of failure [4]. Similarly, studies of politeness in English, such as those by Brown and Levinson, have shown that speakers often employ hedging devices, such as *perhaps*, *maybe*, and *I'll try*, to soften their commitments and reduce the face-threatening impact of their utterances [3].

In addition to the linguistic strategies used in commissive acts, the social and cultural context plays an essential role in shaping their realization. Studies by Chen and Holmes have emphasized the importance of social norms in determining how commitment is expressed and interpreted [5, 4]. For example, in formal settings such as business negotiations or professional interactions, speakers tend to use more indirect and cautious forms of commissive acts to avoid making overly strong or binding commitments. In contrast, in informal settings, speakers may be more direct and confident in their promises or offers, as they are less concerned with the social consequences of failure.

Furthermore, the role of power dynamics in the realization of commissive acts has been explored by various scholars. For instance, Yule noted that the hierarchical relationship between interlocutors can influence the degree of directness or indirectness in the commissive acts they

perform [6]. In contexts where power differences exist (e.g., between a manager and an employee), speakers may use indirect strategies or hedging to maintain politeness and avoid appearing overly dominant or imposing.

Overall, the literature suggests that commissive speech acts in English are shaped by a combination of linguistic, social, and contextual factors. The study of these acts provides valuable insights into how speakers navigate social relationships and manage their commitments through language. This article seeks to expand on this body of work by focusing specifically on the communicative-pragmatic features of commissive acts in English, with an emphasis on the linguistic strategies used and the influence of context on their realization and interpretation.

Results. The analysis of the communicative-pragmatic features of commissive speech acts in English revealed a variety of linguistic strategies and contextual influences shaping how these acts are realized. The findings highlight both the forms of commissive speech acts used by English speakers and the underlying pragmatic considerations, such as politeness, social context, and the degree of commitment involved. The following sections present the results in relation to the key factors identified in the study: linguistic strategies, hedging, modality, and the role of context in determining the realization of commissive acts.

The data analysis revealed that English speakers use a combination of direct and indirect strategies when performing commissive speech acts. Direct forms of commissives, such as promises and offers, were predominantly realized using modal verbs like *will*, *shall*, and *can*, often in simple future tense constructions (e.g., "I will help you" or "I'll send the report tomorrow"). This finding aligns with Searle's definition of commissive acts, where the speaker makes an explicit commitment to perform a future action [2]. These direct forms were most frequently used in informal settings, where the relationship between the speaker and listener was familiar and the social stakes were relatively low.

Indirect strategies, on the other hand, involved the use of conditional constructions, hedging devices, and modal verbs that softened the commitment expressed in the utterance. For instance, speakers often used conditional clauses (e.g., "If you need help, I can assist you") or modal verbs in a less assertive form (e.g., "I might be able to help"). These indirect forms were more prevalent in formal contexts, such as business meetings or professional correspondence, where the speaker sought to avoid making strong, binding commitments. This finding supports Holmes' observation that English speakers often use hedging to mitigate the force of their speech acts and maintain social harmony, especially in situations where failure to fulfill a commitment could have negative consequences [4].

Hedging emerged as a significant pragmatic strategy in the realization of commissive speech acts in English. Hedging was found to be particularly common in both formal and online communication, where speakers were more likely to use phrases like *maybe*, *perhaps*, or *I'll try* to soften the strength of their promises or offers. For example, in a business email, a speaker might write, "I'll try to get back to you by the end of the day," instead of the more direct "I will get back to you by the end of the day". This use of hedging reflects an effort to express commitment while maintaining flexibility and avoiding the potential face-threatening impact of a firm promise.

This finding is consistent with the work of Brown and Levinson, who argue that hedging is a common politeness strategy used to protect the speaker's face by mitigating the force of an utterance [3]. In the case of commissive speech acts, hedging allows the speaker to commit to an

action without taking full responsibility, especially in situations where the action may not be fully within the speaker's control or when there is uncertainty about the outcome.

The analysis also highlighted the role of modality in expressing varying degrees of commitment. Modal verbs such as *will*, *may*, *might*, and *could* were frequently used to indicate different levels of certainty and commitment. Stronger commitments were often expressed using the modal *will* (e.g., "I will help you"), while weaker, more tentative commitments involved modals like *might* or *could* (e.g., "I could help you" or "I might be able to help"). These modal variations reflect a speaker's attempt to balance the strength of their commitment with their ability to fulfill the promise, as well as the social expectations surrounding the speech act.

This finding is in line with Holmes' discussion of how modality influences the interpretation of commissive speech acts [4]. By adjusting the modal verb used, speakers can control the level of assertiveness in their commitment, allowing for a more flexible and context-sensitive communication strategy. For instance, the use of *might* or *could* can serve to reduce the face-threatening impact of a commissive act, which is especially important in formal or professional contexts where the speaker wishes to maintain social harmony and avoid making promises that might be difficult to keep.

The results also demonstrated the significant role of social context in shaping how commissive speech acts are realized in English. In informal, familiar settings - such as among friends or family members - speakers tended to use more direct forms of commissives, often with little to no hedging. For instance, a speaker might simply say, "I'll do it tomorrow" without any qualification. This directness reflects the lower social distance and greater informality characteristic of such interactions, where commitment is expected and easily understood.

In contrast, in formal settings, such as professional meetings or business negotiations, speakers were more likely to use hedging, conditional forms, or indirect language to express commitment. Phrases like "I'll try to" or "It's possible that I can" were common in these contexts, reflecting a more cautious approach to making promises. This pattern is consistent with the findings of Brown and Levinson, who suggest that politeness strategies, including hedging and indirectness, are used to mitigate the potential threat to face when making a commitment in a more formal or hierarchical context [3].

The analysis also revealed that online communication often involved more indirect and hedged forms of commissive speech acts compared to face-to-face interactions. This is particularly evident in email and text message communication, where speakers may employ hedging strategies to account for the lack of nonverbal cues and the potential for miscommunication. For example, in an email to a colleague, a speaker might say, "I'll try to finish the report by tomorrow, but I can't guarantee it" - a phrase that introduces uncertainty and flexibility, minimizing the potential for misunderstanding or unmet expectations. This tendency to hedge in online communication aligns with the findings of Derks and others, who argue that the medium of communication influences the degree of indirectness and hedging used by speakers [7].

In addition to the social context, the study also found that specific communicative situations influenced the formality and strength of the commissive act. In customer service interactions, for instance, employees used hedged promises to avoid over-committing to a customer's expectations (e.g., "I will check on that for you, but I cannot guarantee an immediate resolution"). This reflects the need for service providers to maintain a balance between appearing helpful and avoiding the risk of over-promising.

In political speeches, speakers often used indirect commissive acts to express support for initiatives without making explicit commitments, as seen in the frequent use of modal verbs such as *may* and *might* (e.g., "We may consider this proposal" or "We might move forward with this plan"). This cautious language reflects the highly strategic nature of political communication, where the speaker's public image and the potential for future negotiation must be carefully managed.

Overall, the results of this study demonstrate that commissive speech acts in English are highly context-dependent, with speakers adjusting their linguistic strategies - such as modality, hedging, and directness - according to the social dynamics and the level of formality in the interaction. The findings align with previous research on politeness strategies and modality, highlighting the flexibility of English speakers in navigating commitment in various communicative contexts [3,4].

Discussion. The findings from this study offer valuable insights into the communicative-pragmatic features of commissive speech acts in English language, highlighting the intricate ways in which language users negotiate their commitments in various social contexts. The results not only confirm existing theoretical frameworks in speech act theory but also provide a deeper understanding of how politeness strategies, modality, hedging, and the social context influence the realization and interpretation of commissives. This section discusses the implications of these findings in relation to the broader theoretical landscape of pragmatics, speech act theory, and cross-cultural variation.

One of the key findings of this study is the prevalence of both direct and indirect strategies in the realization of commissive speech acts. As noted, direct forms such as "I will help you" are frequently used in informal settings, where speakers have a closer social relationship and the stakes are low. This aligns with Searle's conceptualization of commissive acts as explicit commitments to future actions [2]. The use of directness reflects the trust and familiarity between interlocutors in these settings, where the speaker feels confident that the commitment will be understood and accepted without ambiguity.

However, in more formal or professional contexts, speakers tend to employ indirect strategies, such as hedging or using conditional clauses (e.g., "If you need help, I might assist you"). This finding is consistent with Brown and Levinson's and Holmes' and theories of politeness, which emphasize the need to mitigate the force of speech acts in situations where social norms dictate a higher degree of formality or caution [3, 4]. Indirectness allows the speaker to protect face and avoid committing too strongly, thus reducing the risk of face-threatening acts or failure to fulfill promises. The use of indirectness in these contexts suggests that English speakers, like speakers of other languages, use pragmatic strategies to navigate the balance between commitment and politeness, which is particularly important in hierarchical or professional settings.

Hedging emerged as a significant feature of commissive speech acts in English, especially in contexts where speakers wish to express their intentions without fully committing to them. The frequent use of modal verbs like *might*, *could*, and *may* was evident, especially in formal and business communication. This finding supports the claims of Brown and Levinson and Holmes, who argue that hedging is a common strategy used to soften the illocutionary force of speech acts [3, 4]. In the case of commissives, hedging allows the speaker to maintain flexibility, which is particularly useful in situations where the speaker may not be entirely certain of their ability to fulfill the commitment or when the outcome is subject to change.

In contrast, stronger modal expressions, such as *will*, were more common in informal, low-stakes interactions, where the speaker felt confident in their ability to fulfill the promise or offer. The relationship between modality and commitment aligns with the observations of Holmes regarding how speakers use modal verbs to signal different degrees of certainty [4]. By modulating the strength of their commitment, speakers can manage their social face and negotiate their involvement in future actions. This dynamic demonstrates how modality serves as a pragmatic tool to convey varying levels of commitment, depending on the interpersonal and situational context.

The social context played a crucial role in shaping how commissive speech acts were realized, with formal contexts favoring more indirect forms and hedging, and informal contexts allowing for greater directness and certainty in promises and offers. This finding is consistent with the sociolinguistic theories of politeness by Brown and Levinson, which highlight how speakers adjust their language to accommodate different social distances and power dynamics [3]. In professional settings, where power relations are more pronounced, speakers often use indirect language to avoid imposing on others or making overbearing commitments. For example, in business meetings, phrases like "I'll try to get back to you" or "I can help, but I may need more time" reflect a cautious approach, acknowledging the limits of the speaker's control over the situation and signaling respect for the interlocutor's expectations.

In contrast, in informal conversations, speakers use more direct commissive acts, as the relational dynamics are typically less hierarchical and there is less perceived risk in making firm commitments. The findings also corroborate Yule's observations on the influence of power relationships on speech act realization, where speakers in positions of power may adopt more direct forms, while those in lower-status positions tend to hedge or mitigate their commitments [6]. This pattern is evident in the corpus of customer service interactions, where employees often hedge promises to avoid over-committing, as customer satisfaction and managing expectations are key concerns.

The study's inclusion of online communication, such as emails and text messages, revealed a significant trend toward indirectness and hedging in the realization of commissive speech acts. Given the lack of nonverbal cues and the increased potential for misinterpretation in digital communication, speakers appear to rely more heavily on hedging strategies to express commitment with caution. This finding is in line with the work of Derks and others, who found that online communication often leads to more indirectness due to the limited ability to convey tone and intent [7].

In email correspondence, for instance, speakers were more likely to use phrases like *I'll try* or *I'll see if I can* to mitigate the potential risks of not fulfilling the commitment. This use of hedging can be seen as a pragmatic strategy to preserve face and maintain flexibility in a medium where social cues are minimized. The findings suggest that the medium of communication - whether face-to-face or digital - can significantly affect how commitment is expressed and perceived, with online communication encouraging more cautious and indirect speech acts to manage uncertainty.

While this study focused on English language, the findings have broader implications for understanding the cross-cultural variation in the realization of commissive speech acts. Research by Chen and other scholars on cross-cultural pragmatics suggests that the realization of commissive speech acts varies across cultures [5]. For example, speakers from cultures with a high value on politeness (e.g., East Asian cultures) may employ more indirect language and hedging

compared to English speakers, who, in certain contexts, may prioritize efficiency and clarity over face-saving. The findings from this study provide a benchmark for comparing English with other languages, particularly in examining how social hierarchies, politeness, and relational dynamics influence the way speakers commit to future actions.

This study has provided a comprehensive analysis of the communicative-pragmatic features of commissive speech acts in English, highlighting the complex interplay between linguistic strategies, modality, hedging, and social context. The findings underscore the dynamic nature of speech acts and the importance of context in determining how commitments are expressed and interpreted. By exploring the nuances of directness, hedging, and modality in different communicative settings, the study contributes to a deeper understanding of the role of language in managing social relationships and negotiating future actions.

Future research could expand this investigation by including a wider range of languages and contexts, allowing for cross-linguistic comparisons that could enrich our understanding of how different cultures realize and interpret commissive speech acts. Furthermore, examining the role of nonverbal cues in face-to-face interactions versus digital communication could provide further insights into how commitment is conveyed and perceived in varying communicative environments.

Conclusion. This study has explored the communicative-pragmatic features of commissive speech acts in English language, providing a detailed analysis of how speakers negotiate commitment through various linguistic strategies, including directness, hedging, and modality. The findings underscore the dynamic and context-sensitive nature of commissive speech acts, demonstrating that the form and strength of commitments vary according to social context, power dynamics, and the medium of communication.

The communicative-pragmatic features of commissive speech acts in English language reveal a complex interplay between intent, context, and social dynamics. Commissives, as fundamental components of communication, function not only to express the speaker's commitment to future actions but also to manage interpersonal relationships and social expectations. Understanding their pragmatic features - such as directness, politeness strategies, and the influence of contextual factors - enhances our comprehension of how language serves both communicative and relational purposes. This analysis underscores the importance of considering pragmatic theory when studying speech acts and highlights the role of cultural and contextual nuances in shaping effective communication.

In conclusion, this research has advanced our understanding of commissive speech acts in English, providing insights into the pragmatic strategies employed by speakers to navigate their social worlds.

The role of hedging, modality, and social context in shaping the realization of commitments underscores the need for a nuanced approach to understanding speech acts. Future studies could extend this research by examining commissive speech acts across different languages and cultures, providing a more comprehensive picture of the cross-linguistic and cross-cultural variation in the realization of commitment.

Additionally, exploring the impact of nonverbal communication in face-to-face interactions and its comparison with digital communication could deepen our understanding of how commitments are conveyed in various communicative contexts.

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